

THE APPLICATION OF ®ClassPoint TOOL IN ENHANCING STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE IN SCIENCE 10

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The Application of @Classpoint Tool in Enhancing Students' Engagement and Performance in Science 10

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Abstract

The application of the @ClassPoint tool is used as an intervention strategy to enhance students' engagement and learning performance. This study aims to determine whether the application of the @ClassPoint tool to science enhances both students' engagement and learning performance. Subsequently, it also determines the correlation between students' engagement and their learning performance. The study utilizes descriptive and quasi-experimental research designs. Experimental (with the use of @ClassPoint) and control group (with conventional teaching) designs were used by 93 Grade 10 students of Kalamansig National High School in the Second Quarter of the School Year 2022-2023. It utilized a simple random sampling technique using the lottery method. Data were gathered through questionnaires and the conduct of pre- and post-tests. Data were analyzed through mean gain, t-test, Pearson correlation, and Cohen's d analyses. Results demonstrate students' engagement with t and p values in the experimental group higher than in the control group. The students' engagement positively and strongly correlates with their learning performance. Cohen's d analyses show that @ClassPoint intervention has a "large effect" in the post-test performance of the experimental group. These results show that is highly significant compared to the control group, with the obtained t-value of 4.894 and a d-value of 0.89, which is described as "large effect". The application of @Classpoint tool in Science 10 instruction enhances both students' engagement and learning performance.

Keywords: *learning engagement, academic performance and @classpoint*

Introduction

Students' engagement is a vital part to make teaching and learning possible. It is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon that is considered a critical factor in supporting students' learning and development. It is attainable with the application of appropriate teaching methodology to make learning interesting. It can influence the learning performance expressed through students' critical thinking skills and retention (Kahu, 2013; Waldrop, Reschly, Fraysier & Appleton 2019).

In creating and crafting activities, students' learning performance must be considered and prioritized. It is reflected through their attainment of higher participation in class discussion, hand-on exercises in the laboratory, achieving high scores in quizzes and scientific reports. It is measured through their improvement of their science process skills. Further, it is manifested in their attitude towards science learning (Safaah, Muslim & Liliawati, 2017).

Science learning engagement and performance are possibly attainable with the application of interactive digital activities, one of which is the Classroom Response System (CRS) as have been reported for the English languages (Abdelrady, 2022). To facilitate student engagement, this Classroom Response System is one of those well-known teaching strategy (Fies & Marshall, 2006; Kay & LeSage, 2009) for the languages, however, not well-documented for the Sciences.

The @ClassPoint tool is a form of CRS technology that is used in this study, being the first time for the Sciences. This @ClassPoint tool is integrated as an approach in teaching with the purpose of enhancing students' engagement and performance in Science 10.

@ClassPoint is a Classroom Response System (CRS) which can be integrated in Microsoft PowerPoint that will make your presentations into an interactive one. It can create quizzes within the PowerPoint presentation without the difficulty of changing into another application during the teaching process. It includes several features such as different modes of questions: the polls, multiple-choice and short type questions. It allows students to answer the instructor-posed question in class and instantly gives feedback to the students. Herein, the application of @ClassPoint Tool is an avenue in conditioning and setting the minds of the students to engage more on assigned activities.

Research Objectives

This study investigates the application of @ClassPoint Tool on the engagement and performance of Grade-10 students in science for the academic year 2022-2023. Particularly, the study:

1. Compares the learning engagement of the experimental and control groups of student-respondents.
2. Compares the test performances of the experimental and control groups of student-respondents.
3. Determines whether or not the use of @classpoint activities improves the test performance of the experimental group of student-respondents;
4. Assesses the relationship between students' engagement and performance.

Literature Review

There are many approaches that have been used by the teachers to integrate in class to address the low performance of the students in science; multimedia has been utilized by some teachers to make the lesson become interesting, some have applied collaborative learning, some have used improvised workbooks purposely to make science easier to understand while others have employed puzzles and games. Choosing and picking the right teaching approach helps in getting the students to participate and engage in class discussion.

Learning Engagement

Making the students engaged in learning helps them to perform well in their lessons, invested on their desire to learn or involved in any class activities, and prepared to put out the effort required by their teachers. The application of appropriate instructional activities contributes on students' engagement, they can have a more complete understanding of the different teaching dynamic than the traditional methods of evaluating the effectiveness of instruction, these includes; student mastery of the course's learning objectives, retention, and perceptions of satisfaction. Teachers can modify instructional approaches by tracking the levels of student engagement to address the students' change in motivation, involvement, and attitude toward their courses and educational goals (Mandernach et al., 2011).

Technology

Parallel to this focus on students' participation, digital literacy and ICT skills are becoming increasingly important on a global scale. Digital technology has become an integral part in higher education, impacting students in a variety of ways.

The integration of technology in class has the capacity to make learning more engaging for students (Chen, Lambert, & Guidry, 2010; Rashid & Asghar, 2016), intensify teaching-learning processes (Kerres, 2013). It can enhance students' self-regulation and self-efficacy, and increase participation in courses and the larger university community.

Improvements in achievement, persistence, and retention have been linked to student engagement, whereas disengagement affects cognitive growth and learning results (Ma, Han, Yang, & Cheng, 2015). According to studies, using technology has a good impact on students. Technology integration can make a creative, interesting, and engaging learning if is extensively implemented (Arrieta, 2020). Another study found that, in comparison to traditional teaching techniques, using technology to teach science courses boosted student engagement in the learning process, improved student accomplishment scores, and made it easier for students to complete their homework (Nawzad, & Said, 2018).

Not only do technology-integrated teaching methods make pedagogical approaches more creative, but they also support learners' cognitive development, boost satisfaction, encourage engagement, enhance the value of assessments, offer immediate feedback, and improve desired learning behaviors and academic performance.

The implementation of Classroom Response System in the classroom has become simpler as a result of recent technological developments and device accessibility. Mobile gadgets and computer-based Classroom Response Systems like Kahoot!, Learning Catalytics and Mentimeter are now examples of technology that allow anonymous responses, which encourages timid and hesitant students who would otherwise choose not to participate in class activities. The use of a Classroom Response System, allows the teachers to input questions beforehand and have students respond to them in class while using their own personal devices. It is a technique that increases student engagement with clicker technology, which provides immediate and formative assessment throughout class (Fies & Marshall, 2006; Kay & LeSage, 2009). Its quick feedback on student responses enables the teacher to track and instantly access students' grasp of the course content and offering the teachers the chance to explain any concepts that the students did not understand (Caldwell, 2007).

The effectiveness of an interactive digital tool like the @ClassPoint tool is being examined in English as a Foreign Language students' learning satisfaction. Results showed that the learning satisfaction of EFL students using @ClassPoint was much higher than that of EFL students not using @ClassPoint, which supports the effectiveness of @ClassPoint tool in enhancing students' learning satisfaction in English as a Foreign Language (Abdelrady et al., 2022).

@ClassPoint Tool

The interactive and motivating features of the @ClassPoint application in the educational setting can be taken into account as one of the factors that contribute in strengthening student's learning satisfaction. It can help students maintain their attention during e-learning activities (Lee et al. ,2019).

According to surveys, greater than 80% of the students agreed that @ClassPoint is a powerful tool for encouraging student involvement and participation in the classroom. A majority of educators (60%) agreed and 40% of the pupils strongly agreed that they responded the interactive quizzes supplied via @ClassPoint more frequently than they do to verbal responses in class.

Overall, both teachers and students appreciated using @ClassPoint because it encourages participation from students throughout both online and in-person courses (Bong & Chatterjee, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive and quasi-experimental research designs. The descriptive was used to determine the engagement level of Science 10 learners; while the experimental design allowed the study to compare the difference of pre-assessment test performance and post-assessment test performance of the learners in Science 10 which uses @ClassPoint as a teaching approach.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 10 Junior High School students of Kalamansig National High School. The group was specified as experimental group, while the other group was known as control group. The experimental group consists of 47 students while the other group which is the control group comprised of 46 students.

Simple random sampling technique was done through lottery method. Two sections of students from the Junior High School of Kalamansig National High School were chosen to serve as the control and experimental group, respectively. The control group which consists of 46 learners taught with conventional way of teaching while the experimental group which consist of 47 learners taught with an intervention strategy; the @ClassPoint application tool.

Instrument

The interactive method of teaching delivery was administered in this study, the interactive class discussion and game activities with @ClassPoint was used as a tool to begin the class session in the motivation part through different question types, such as brief answers, multiple choice questions and quick poll. The students were given class code of @ClassPoint by the teacher so that students can participate in the interactive quizzes. These was integrated in PowerPoint during class discussion as an interactive presentation tool enabling learners to have a great understanding of the concept. The content of the lessons were aligned to (MELCS) Most Essential Learning Competencies of the K-12 curriculum.

Afterward, in a similar way, commencing the discussion by letting the students have a group activity was an avenue to cooperative learning. Then, at the end of the class an interactive quiz competition was held which gives rewards and acknowledges the students who was on the top of the leaderboard in answering the interactive quiz competition.

The Standardized test was used in order to gauge and analyze the scientific ability of the learners in Science 10 - Physics. Both groups took the pre assessment test in the beginning of the study and at the end of the four (4) weeks teaching both the experimental and control group took the post-assessment test in same manner. The assessment test comprised of 30 items multiple choice test made by the researcher were used during the conduct of the pre-assessment and post-assessment test. The questionnaires were formulated and anchored in Bloom's Taxonomy Level of Thinking. It is distributed based on the Table of Specification and were checked and validated by the panel of members. The researcher conducted pilot testing on Grade 11 learners to ensure the reliability of the assessment test. The test questions were analyzed, while the index of discrimination and index of difficulty was determined. The index of discrimination and difficulty of the items were interpreted using the following criterion as adopted from the Model of (Andres, 2011) presented in table 1.

Table 1. *Index of Discrimination*

<i>Index of Discrimination</i>	<i>Item Evaluation</i>
0.31-0.40	Very Good Item
0.21-0.30	Good Item
0.11-0.20	Revise
0 below	Reject

In her study, the Index of Discriminations was interpreted as shown above. Items considered very easy and very difficult having a negative or zero discriminant were rejected. Items considered difficult and easy with positive discriminant were subjected for revision. On the other hand, the good and very good items were retained.

Table 2. *Index of Difficulty of the Test Items*

<i>Index of Difficulty</i>	<i>Item Evaluation</i>
0 – 0.14	Very Difficult
0.15 – 0.39	Difficult
0.40 – 0.70	Average
0.71 – 0.85	Easy
0.86 above	Very Easy

Meanwhile, the Index of Difficulty was interpreted as shown above. The proportion of the students who answered the test item accurately was calculated in order to find the choices that should be replaced and revised. In addition, to determine the students' level of engagement between the groups, the questionnaire was adjusted to fit the context of the investigation before data collection for the current study began. The questionnaire's modified form included a 20-item questions that seeks to know the students' level of engagement towards science with the integration of interactive presentation and games with @ClassPoint. Pre-assessment and post-

assessment tests results was analyzed using the Mean Percentage Score (MPS).

The questionnaire was utilized to gather information about the engagement level of the students. The Students' Level of Engagement was measured using the descriptive survey questionnaire.

Procedure

Upon the approval of the advisory committee, a request letter addressed to the dean of the MSU-Maguindanao Graduate School, Office of the Sultan Kudarat Division and the Principal of Kalamansig National High School was sent. After the approval of the request, the researcher oriented the class advisers of the Grade 10 students regarding the nature of the study and the students had an orientation of the procedure and concept/flow of the study. Afterwards they had given an assent form to secure affirmation that they are willing to participate and be a subject of the study.

Before the actual conduct of the study, the researcher prepared a survey questionnaire form and conducted a pilot test or pre-survey to test the validity of the survey questionnaire. After the ensuing survey questionnaire was proven valid, the researcher proceeded to the collection of the data.

The researcher adapted the survey questionnaire of (Arbaugh, et al. 2008) which was developed a measure that operationalized (Garrison, et al.2000) Community of Inquiry (CoI) Survey framework for creating effective learning environments, which focuses on social and cognitive presence. And the Student Evaluation of Online Teaching Effectiveness (SEOTE) to assessed teaching effectiveness in online contexts with a focus on constructivist-based practices to provide instructors with constructive feedback to improve teaching (Chickering & Gamson, 1987).

Data Analysis

All gathered data was encoded and processed using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) and using the statistical kingdom. Appropriate statistical tools was used in the study such as means, standard deviation, Cohen's d analysis and Pearson's correlation analysis to determine the performance of the respondents in the pre and post assessment test and the correlation of their learning engagement to their academic performance. Likewise, dependent t-test was used to determine whether the difference between mean levels of the pre-assessment test and post assessment test performance in Science 10 was significant or not significant at 0.05 level.

Results and Discussion

The Learning Engagement of the Science 10 – Physics Students

The Learning Engagement of the Control Group of Science 10 - Physics Students

The level of the learning engagement of the control group of Science 10 – Physics students is presented below (Table 3).

Table 3. The learning engagement of the control group of Science 10 - Physics students without the use of @ClassPoint (n=46)

Indicator Statements	Level of Engagement	
	Mean	Description
1. I am motivated to explore content-related questions on qualitative images formed in plane mirror.	3.74	Highly Agree
2. I get more actively involved in learning the different images formed in convex mirror.	3.16	Moderately Agree
3. It allows me to take responsibility for my own learning on the images formed in concave mirror.	3.02	Moderately Agree
4. I get engaged to do my best work in explaining the concepts on law of reflection.	3.16	Moderately Agree
5. I understand the concepts on the uses of mirror in our daily life.	3.21	Moderately Agree
6. I find the instructions easy to follow in determining the characteristics of images formed by curved mirrors.	2.91	Moderately Agree
7. I pay more attention to the teacher's presentation on the concepts of electric motors.	2.95	Moderately Agree
8. The lessons are enjoyable in identifying the electric motors in appliances at home.	3.16	Moderately Agree
9. I enjoy the task in determining if it is a real or virtual image that is formed by the lenses.	3.10	Moderately Agree
10. I enjoy answering paper type quizzes on electric motors.	2.98	Moderately Agree
11. I gather good impressions of my classmate during the group activities.	2.98	Moderately Agree
12. I gain a sense of belongingness in the class.	3.02	Moderately Agree
13. I develop a sense of collaboration with my groupmates during our group activity in images formed in curve mirror.	3.04	Moderately Agree
14. I feel competitive in every quiz presented.	2.98	Moderately Agree
15. I receive my feedback right after the question is asked.	3.11	Moderately Agree
16. I am excited to know my scores presented in board.	3.00	Moderately Agree
17. I am eager when my teacher shows score of our quiz.	2.95	Moderately Agree
18. The activities are structured to be student friendly.	2.89	Moderately Agree
19. It is easy to understand the topics without using my gadgets.	2.89	Moderately Agree
Grand Mean	3.07	Moderately Agree

Legend: 1.00–1.80 – Never Agree, 1.81–2.60 – Slightly Agree, 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree, 3.41–4.20 – Highly Agree, 4.21–5.00 – Extremely Agree

The learning engagement of control group of students has the highest mean of 3.74, which means they “highly agree” being “motivated to explore content-related questions on qualitative images formed in plane mirror (Indicator Statement 1).” It has the lowest mean of 2.89, which means the same group of students “moderately agree” to both “the activities are structured to be student-friendly (Indicator Statement 19)”, and “It is easy to understand the topics without using my gadgets (Indicator Statement 20).” Generally, such learning engagement of the group has a grand mean of 3.07, which means that the students “moderately agree” to the 20 indicator statements. Such performance is attained in a teaching-learning process without the application of @ClassPoint.

Similar results are found by a study where conventional education methods are employed and are found inadequate in meeting the different learning demands. Where the teachers are in the center of the teaching process, most of the learning demands are no longer addressed properly and because the atmosphere is not conducive for the students (Cooper, 2001). Likewise, another study claims that the conventional approach is not the most pertinent teaching strategy in the teaching process (Mokhtar, 2016).

The Learning Engagement of the Experimental Group of Science 10 - Physics Students

The levels of the learning engagement of the experimental groups of Science 10 – Physics students is presented below (Table 4).

Table 4. *The learning engagement of the experimental group of Science 10 -Physics students that uses @ClassPoint (n=47)*

Indicator Statements	Level of Engagement	
	Mean	Description
1. I am motivated to explore content related questions on qualitative images formed in plane mirror.	4.17	Highly Agree
2. I got more actively involved in learning the different images formed in convex mirror.	4.19	Highly Agree
3. It allowed me to take responsibility for my own learning on the images formed in concave mirror.	4.02	Highly Agree
4. I get engaged to do my best work in explaining the concepts on law of reflection.	4.04	Highly Agree
5. I understand the concepts on the uses of mirror in our daily life.	4.38	Extremely Agree
6. I found the instructions easy to follow in determining the characteristics of images formed by curved mirrors.	4.23	Extremely Agree
7. I pay more attention to the teacher’s presentation on the concepts of electric motors.	4.34	Extremely Agree
8. The lessons are enjoyable in identifying the electric motors in appliances at home.	4.30	Extremely Agree
9. I enjoyed the task in determining if it is a real or virtual image that is formed by the lenses.	4.34	Extremely Agree
10. I enjoyed answering the quizzes on electric motors presented in polls.	4.13	Highly Agree
11. I experienced greater interaction with my classmates as we identify simple electric generators.	4.23	Extremely Agree
12. I gather good impressions of my classmate during the interactive activities.	4.21	Extremely Agree
13. I gain a sense of belongingness in the class.	4.17	Highly Agree
14. I developed a sense of collaboration with my groupmates during our group activity in images formed in curve mirror.	4.30	Extremely Agree
15. I feel competitive in every quiz presented.	4.19	Highly Agree
16. I received my feedback right after the question is asked.	4.28	Extremely Agree
17. I am excited to know my scores presented in leaderboard.	4.26	Extremely Agree
18. I am eager when the leaderboard shows score of our quiz.	4.09	Highly Agree
19. The activities are structured to be student friendly.	4.21	Extremely Agree
20. It is very easy to use in my own gadgets.	4.13	Highly Agree
Grand Mean	4.21	Extremely Agree

Legend: 1.00–1.80 – Never Agree, 1.81–2.60 – Slightly Agree, 2.61–3.40 – Moderately Agree, 3.41–4.20 – Highly Agree, 4.21–5.00 – Extremely Agree

The learning engagement of the experimental group of students has the highest mean of 4.38, which means they “extremely agree” to “understand the concepts on the uses of mirror in our daily life (Indicator Statement 5).” It has the lowest mean of 4.02, which means such experimental group of students “highly agree” to being “allowed to take responsibility for my own learning on the images formed in concave mirror (Indicator Statement 5).” Generally, such learning engagement of the group has a grand mean of 4.21, which means that the students “extremely agree” to the 20 indicator statements. Such performance is attained in a teaching-learning process with the use of the @ClassPoint application.

Similar results are found by a study where higher than 80% of the student-participants assert that @ClassPoint is an effective means of encouraging students’ involvement and engagement in the classroom (Bong and Chatterje, 2021). In another study, the results prove that after using @ClassPoint as intervention materials, the students’ level of performance increased; and that the @ClassPoint has an affirmative effect on student’s performance (Yusi, 2023).

The Comparison of the Learning Engagement of the Control and Experimental Groups of Grade 10 – Physics Students

The levels of the learning engagement between the control and experimental groups of Science 10 – Physics students are compared below (Table 5).

The mean of the learning engagement of the control group is 3.07 with an SD of 0.80941 which is described as “moderately agree,” while, the mean of the experimental group is 4.21 with an SD of 0.55030 which is described as “extremely agree.” Generally, the Science 10 - Physics students of the control group moderately agree that they have a moderate level of engagement as they engage in learning using the conventional method of teaching while those of the experimental group extremely agree that they have extreme level

of engagement in the learning process with the use of the application @ClassPoint.

Table 5. *The levels of the learning engagement between the control and experimental groups of Science 10- Physics students (n = 93)*

Group	SD	Levels of Engagement	
		Mean	Interpretation
Control	0.80941	3.07	Moderately Agree
Experimental	0.55030	4.21	Extremely Agree

Positive results of one study shows that active engagement in learning has a positive effect on both grades and other skills such as critical thinking skills (Ackerman et. al.,2003). The same findings are found by another study that encouraging students and putting them in engaging situation during class could increase their willingness to study and help them remember what they've been taught (Khozaei, Zare & Moneghi, 2022).

T-test Analysis on Learning Engagement of Control and Experimental Group

The t-test analysis of the learning engagement between the control and experimental groups of Science 10 – Physics students are compared below (Table 6).

Table 6. *T-test analysis on the learning engagement of control and experimental group of Science 10- Physics students (n = 93)*

Group	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Control	3.07	0.80941	-4.362	0.000
Experimental	4.21	0.55030		

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

The mean of the learning engagement of the control group is 3.07 with an SD of 0.80941 while the mean of the experimental group is 4.21 with an SD of 0.55030. The obtained t-value of t is -4.362 with a probability of $0.000 < 0.05$ level of significance. Generally, the result shows that there is a significant difference between the learning engagement of the experimental and control groups. This implies that the experimental group expresses higher level of engagement than of the control group.

The results of this study, which show a strong and positive association between engagement and academic achievement, are consistent with those of several prior studies (Sbrocco, 2009; Scheidler, 2012). In a similar context, students perform better on standardized tests are more engaged in class discussion. From a higher perspective, some research assert that motivated students produce better academic results (Fredricks et al., 2004; Adelman & Taylor, 2010).

Levels of Students' Performance in the Pre-test and Post- test

The Levels of Performance in the Pre - test and Post-test of the Control Group of Science 10 - Physics Students

The levels of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test of the control group of Science 10- Physics students are shown below (Table 7).

Table 7. *The levels of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test of the control group of Science 10- Physics students*

Indicator Statements	Level of Students' Performance			
	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
1. Which term refers to the width of a spherical mirror?	5	Does Not Meet Expectation	20	Nearly Meets Expectation
2. When the image of an object is observed in a plane mirror, what type of images will form?	18	Nearly Meets Expectation	17	Nearly Meets Expectation
3. Which statement below best describes an incident ray?	11	Nearly Meets Expectation	8	Nearly Meets Expectation
4. Which of the following letter denotes the center of the curvature?	13	Nearly Meets Expectation	23	Nearly Meets Expectation
5. What kind of mirror is used by department stores to give a wider area and smaller image of the shoppers/buyers?	14	Nearly Meets Expectation	24	Meets Expectation
6. Which example of a mirror is illustrated on the right?	12	Nearly Meets Expectation	34	Meets Expectation
7. Which mirror concept explains why the word AMBULANCE is written in reverse in an ambulance car?	17	Nearly Meets Expectation	25	Meets Expectation
8. What type of mirror was used by dentists in examining tooth cavities?	28	Meets Expectation	34	Meets Expectation
9. Vehicle's side mirrors are examples of what type of mirrors?	16	Nearly Meets Expectation	27	Meets Expectation
10. Which of the following parts of the eyes function like the aperture and iris diaphragm of a camera?	17	Nearly Meets Expectation	21	Nearly Meets Expectation
11. What tool is used by astronomers to see faraway objects?	29	Meets Expectation	33	Meets Expectation

12. Which of the following is a correct ray diagram for convex lens?	7	Does Not Meet Expectation	30	Meets Expectation	
13. In the photograph illustrated on the right, the water droplet is acting like a lens. How does the lens work?	4	Does Not Meet Expectation	23	Nearly Meets Expectation	
14. What is the nature of the image formed in the magnifying glass?	27	Meets Expectation	17	Nearly Meets Expectation	
15. Which of the following statement tells the difference between lenses and mirrors?	25	Meets Expectation	27	Meets Expectation	
16. The diagram below shows an object placed in front of a concave lens. What are the characteristics of the image formed?	8	Does Not Meet Expectation	17	Nearly Meets Expectation	
17. The sun's rays are observed to focus at a point behind a lens. What kind of lens was used?	9	Does Not Meet Expectation	8	Does Not Meet Expectation	
18. What will be the appearance of an arm-length object when someone is looking through a concave lens?	13	Nearly Meets Expectation	3	Does Not Meet Expectation	
19. Which statement is NOT correct about the distinctive attribute of an electrical generator?	5	Does Not Meet Expectation	25	Meets Expectation	
20. What is a huge wheel that rotates when driven by water?	22	Nearly Meets Expectation	20	Nearly Meets Expectation	
21. Which of the following is in a correct sequence in the operation of a simple motor?	10	Does Not Meet Expectation	21	Nearly Meets Expectation	
22. What two forces are required to operate generators and electric motors?	22	Nearly Meets Expectation	36	Exceeds Expectation	
23. Who invented the first generator?	8	Does Not Meet Expectation	29	Meets Expectation	
24. Who discovered that a magnetic field can produce electric current?	26	Meets Expectation	35	Exceeds Expectation	
25. Which device converts electrical energy into mechanical energy?	3	Does Not Meet Expectation	9	Does Not Meet Expectation	
26. Which statement best describes the operation of an electrical motor?	12	Nearly Meets Expectation	13	Nearly Meets Expectation	
27. What are the two types of (DC) direct current motors?	6	Does Not Meet Expectation	14	Nearly Meets Expectation	
28. What are the three basic parts of an electric generator?	11	Does Not Meet Expectation	3	Does Not Meet Expectation	
29. Which of the following is a function of commutator in a generator?	12	Does Not Meet Expectation	16	Nearly Meets Expectation	
30. What mechanism can generate electrical current when a wire coil is wrapped around an iron core and rotated close to magnet?	14	Nearly Meets Expectation	26	Meets Expectation	
Grand Mean		14.13	Nearly Meets Expectation	21.27	Nearly Meets Expectation

Legend: 1-11 – Does Not Meet Expectation, 12-23 – Nearly Meets Expectation, 24-34 – Meets Expectation, 35-46 – Exceeds Expectation

The level of students' performance of the control group, as reflected in the pre-test, is highest at 29 out of 46 students particularly with the indicator statement "What tool is used by astronomers to see faraway objects?" (Indicator Statement 11) which is described as "meets expectation." It is lowest at 3 with the indicator statement "Which device converts electrical energy into mechanical energy?" (Indicator Statement 25) which is described as "does not yet meet expectation." Generally, the level of performance in the pre-assessment tests have a grand mean of 14.13 out 46 students which is described as "nearly meets expectation."

The level of students' performance of the control group, as reflected in the post-tests, is highest at 36 out of 46 students particularly with the indicator statement "What two forces are required to operate generators and electric motors?" (Indicator Statement 22) which is described as "exceeds expectation." It is lowest at 3 with two indicator statements "What will be the appearance of an arm-length object when someone is looking through a concave lens?" (Indicator Statement 18) and "Which device converts electrical energy into mechanical energy?" (Indicator Statement 28) which are described as "does not meet expectation." Generally, however, the level of students' performance in the post-test has a grand mean of 21.27 which is described as "nearly meets expectation."

The level of students' performance, as reflected by both of the pre-test and post-test results, is obtained with conventional teaching-learning methods, that is, without the application of @ClassPoint. It is rated with a low range of 14.13 to 21.27 and which is described as "nearly meets expectation."

These results demonstrate that conventional teaching, known as teacher-centered, where the teachers are in the center of the teaching and learning process, where most of the learning demands of the students are no longer addressed properly (Cooper, 2001), and that it is not the most relevant teaching strategy in the teaching and learning process (Mokhtar, 2016).

Nowadays, many educators believe that conventional way of teaching is not so effective (Marbach-Ad, Seal, & Sokolove, 2001; Jungst, Licklider, & Wiersema, 2003) that as a result of lectures, learning is relatively superficial and transient (Phipps, Phipps, Kask, & Higgins, 2001; Moust, Van Berkel, & Schmidt, 2005) that allows learners to be passive recipients of information that has been "predigested" by the teacher (Hansen & Stephens, 2000, p. 42).

The Levels of Performance in the Pre-test and Post-test of the Experimental Group of Science 10 - Physics Students

The levels of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group of Science 10- Physics students are presented below (Table 8).

Table 8. *The levels of students' performance in the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group of Science 10- Physics students*

Indicator Statements	Level of Students' Performance			
	Pre-test	Description	Post-test	Description
1. Which term refers to the width of a spherical mirror?	9	Does Not Meet Expectation	40	Exceeds Expectation
2. When the image of an object is observed in a plane mirror, what type of images will form?	16	Nearly Meets Expectation	26	Meets Expectation
3. Which statement below best describes an incident ray?	7	Does Not Meet Expectation	37	Exceeds Expectation
4. Which of the following letter denotes the center of the curvature?	20	Nearly Meets Expectation	40	Exceeds Expectation
5. What kind of mirror is used by department stores to give a wider area and smaller image of the shoppers/buyers?	21	Nearly Meets Expectation	43	Exceeds Expectation
6. Which example of a mirror is illustrated on the right?	20	Nearly Meets Expectation	34	Meets Expectation
7. Which mirror concept explains why the word AMBULANCE is written in reverse in an ambulance car?	20	Nearly Meets Expectation	43	Exceeds Expectation
8. What type of mirror was used by dentists in examining tooth cavities?	21	Nearly Meets Expectation	39	Exceeds Expectation
9. Vehicle's side mirrors are examples of what type of mirrors?	18	Nearly Meets Expectation	36	Exceeds Expectation
10. Which of the following parts of the eyes function like the aperture and iris diaphragm of a camera?	14	Nearly Meets Expectation	20	Meets Expectation
11. What tool is used by astronomers to see faraway objects?	26	Meets Expectation	40	Exceeds Expectation
12. Which of the following is a correct ray diagram for convex lens?	15	Nearly Meet Expectation	33	Meets Expectation
13. In the photograph illustrated on the right, the water droplet is acting like a lens. How does the lens work?	13	Nearly Not Meet Expectation	29	Meets Expectation
14. What is the nature of the image formed in the magnifying glass?	27	Meets Expectation	43	Exceeds Expectation
15. Which of the following statement tells the difference between lenses and mirrors?	23	Nearly Meets Expectation	33	Meets Expectation
16. The diagram below shows an object placed in front of a concave lens. What are the characteristics of the image formed?	15	Nearly Not Meet Expectation	17	Nearly Meets Expectation
17. The sun's rays are observed to focus at a point behind a lens. What kind of lens was used?	11	Does Not Meet Expectation	37	Exceeds Expectation
18. What will be the appearance of an arm-length object when someone is looking through a concave lens?	12	Nearly Meets Expectation	18	Nearly Meets Expectation
19. Which statement is NOT correct about the distinctive attribute of an electrical generator?	8	Does Not Meet Expectation	28	Meets Expectation
20. What is a huge wheel that rotates when driven by water?	16	Nearly Meets Expectation	35	Exceeds Expectation
21. Which of the following is in a correct sequence in the operation of a simple motor?	6	Does Not Meet Expectation	16	Nearly Meets Expectation
22. What two forces are required to operate generators and electric motors?	25	Meets Expectation	35	Exceeds Expectation
23. Who invented the first generator?	4	Does Not Meet Expectation	37	Exceeds Expectation
24. Who discovered that a magnetic field can produce electric current?	27	Meets Expectation	40	Exceeds Expectation
25. Which device converts electrical energy into mechanical energy?	7	Does Not Meet Expectation	10	Does Not Meet Expectation
26. Which statement best describes the operation of an electrical motor?	15	Nearly Meets Expectation	22	Nearly Meets Expectation
27. What are the two types of (DC) direct current motors?	14	Nearly Meets Expectation	16	Nearly Meets Expectation
28. What are the three basic parts of an electric generator?	9	Does Not Meet Expectation	29	Meets Expectation
29. Which of the following is a function of commutator in a generator?	10	Does Not Meet Expectation	22	Nearly Meets Expectation
30. What mechanism can generate electrical current when a wire coil is wrapped around an iron core and rotated close to magnet?	20	Nearly Meets Expectation	30	Meets Expectation
Grand Mean	15.63	Nearly Meets Expectation	30.43	Meets Expectation

Legend: 1-11 – Does Not Meet Expectation, 12-23 – Nearly Meets Expectation, 24-34 – Meets Expectation, 35-46 – Exceeds Expectation

The level of students' performance of the experimental group, as reflected in the pre-test, is highest at 27 out of 46 students particularly with the indicator statement "What is the nature of the image formed in the magnifying glass?" (Indicator Statement 14) which is described as "meets expectation." It is lowest at 4 with the indicator statement "Who invented the first generator?" (Indicator Statement 23) which is described as "does not meet expectation." Generally, however, the level of students' performance in the pre-test has a grand mean of 15.63 which is described as "nearly meets expectation."

The level of students' performance of the experimental group, as reflected in the post-test, is highest at 43 out of 46 students particularly with three indicator statements "What kind of mirror is used by department stores to give a wider area and smaller image of the shoppers/buyers?" (Indicator Statement 5), "Which mirror concept explains why the word AMBULANCE is written in reverse in an ambulance car?" (Indicator Statement 7), and "What is the nature of the image formed in the magnifying glass?" (Indicator Statement 14), which are described as "exceeds expectation." It is lowest at 10 with the indicator statement "Which device converts electrical energy into mechanical energy?" (Indicator Statement 25) and which is described as "does not meet expectation". Generally, however, the level of student performance in the post-tests has a grand mean of 30.43 which is described as "meets expectation."

The level of students' performance of the experimental group is rated as low in the pretest (grand mean = 15.63) which is described as "nearly meets expectation" but is rated as high in the post-test (grand mean = 30.43) which is described as "meets expectation." These post-test results are obtained with the application of @ClassPoint. These results demonstrate that teaching intervened with the @ClassPoint has improved the students' learning performance. As claimed by several studies, students' learning performance increase with the application of @ClassPoint (EY Bong, C Chatterjee, 2021) and using it effectively has a beneficial effect on students' achievement test (Yusi, 2023).

The Comparison of Students' Performance in the Pre-test of the Control and Experimental Groups of Grade 10 – Physics Students

The comparison on the mean level of students' performance in the pre-tests between the control and experimental groups of Science 10 – Physics students is shown in the following analysis below (Table 9).

Table 9. *The Cohen's d analysis on the levels of students' performance in pre-test between the control and experimental groups of Science 10- Physics students (n = 93)*

Group	Mean	SD	t – value	d – value
Pretest- Experimental	3.8333	6.4705	3.245	0.59
Pretest-Control				

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Legend: 0.0 – 0.19 – no effect (negligible), 0.51- 0.80 – medium effect, 0.2- 0.5 – small effect, > 0. 81- large effect

The mean of the students' performances between the control and experimental group is 3.8333 with an SD of 6.4705. The obtained t-value is 3.245 and the d- value is 0.59 which is described as "medium effect". The two groups have closely related levels of performance in their pre-tests. This implies that the two groups of students are relatively not yet exposed to the contents covered on the pre-test before the test was administered to them and they are of closely related levels which make them fit and comparable for the conduct of the study.

A particular study stresses similar findings where its result of the pre-test is a baseline of the performance mean score for both experimental and control groups. It explains that the two samples are classified heterogeneously and are suitable to use as research respondents (Puedan, 2018). Another study confirms that the result of the pre-test of two groups under experimentation had the same level of academic preparation before the conduct of the study (Abdulkarim, 2016).

The Comparison of the Post-Test Performance of Control and Experimental Group

The comparison on the mean level of students' performance in the post-tests between the control and experimental groups of Science 10 – Physics students is shown in the following analysis below (Table 10).

Table 10. *The Cohen's d analysis on the post-test mean gain of control and experimental groups of Science 10- Physics students (n = 93)*

Group	Mean	SD	t – value	d – value
Posttest- Experimental	9.16667	10.25900	4.894	0.89
Posttest-Control				

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Legend: 0.0 – 0.19 – no effect (negligible), 0.51- 0.80 – medium effect, 0.2- 0.5 – small effect, > 0. 81- large effect

The mean of the students' performances between the control and experimental group is 9.16667 and an SD of 10.25900. The obtained t-value is 4.894 and the d-value is 0.89 which is described as "large effect." The two groups have different results as to the post-tests given to them and that their difference is highly significant. These results demonstrate the higher student performance of the experimental group that especially received the intervention of @ClassPoint. Also, these results imply that the experimental group performed better and developed the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding in the subject Science 10- Physics with the intervention. Meanwhile, the control group students learned minimum knowledge, skills and understanding in the subject Science 10-

Physics, especially without any intervention.

The results of this study are similar to the findings of an earlier study that stresses the post-test scores obtained by the students in experimental group is significantly different from the post-test scores obtained by the students in control group after the conduct of experimentation (Zengin et al., 2011). Likewise, another study proves that after using @ClassPoint as intervention materials, the students' level of performance increased; and that the @ClassPoint has an affirmative effect on student's performance (Yusi, 2023). Similarly, another empirical evidence which confirms that integrating @ClassPoint tool activities into the learning environment significantly enhances students' learning satisfaction when compared to the non-ClassPoint-integrated learning mode (Abdelrady et al., 2022).

Analysis on the Improvement of the Test Performance of Experimental Group

The analysis on the improvement (in terms of mean gain) from pretest to post test of the experimental group of Science 10 – Physics students is shown below (Table 11).

Table 11. *The Cohen's d analysis on pre-test and post-test mean gain of experimental group of Science 10- Physics students (n=47)*

Experimental Group	Mean	SD	t – value	d- value
Posttest-mean gain Pretest-mean gain	26.5250	22.1653	6.555	1.20

$\alpha=0.05$ level of significance

Legend: 0.0 – 0.19 – no effect (negligible), 0.51- 0.80 – medium effect, 0.2- 0.5 – small effect, > 0. 81- large effect

The pre- test and post-test mean gain of the students in the experimental group is 26.5250 and an SD of 22.1653. The obtained t –value is 6.555 with a d-value of 1.20 which is described as “large effect.” These results indicate that the mean gain difference is highly significant. Also, these results imply that the integration of the teaching intervention, the @ClassPoint, make a significant impact on the performance of the students.

The results of this study are similar to the findings of another study which affirm that after the utilization of @ClassPoint in teaching and learning process, the said intervention is effective and has a beneficial effect on student's achievement on the test (Yusi, 2023). Likewise, in another study it is claimed that the more students are engaged in class, the more their achievement are likely to increase (Peters et al., 2019; Bond, 2000).

Correlation of Learning Engagement and Post-test Performance of Control Group

The Pearson Correlation analysis between the learning engagement and the post-test performance of the control group of Science 10 – Physics students is presented (Table 12).

Table 12. *The Pearson Correlation analysis of the learning engagement and post-test performance of control group without the use of @ClassPoint (n=46)*

Control Group	r- value	p-value
Learning Engagement Post Test	0.659	0.000

$\alpha=0.01$ level of correlation

The learning engagement and post-test performance of the control group has an r-value of 0.659 and a p-value of .000 that is lesser than 0.01 level of correlation. These results indicate that there is a significant relationship between the learning engagement and post-test performance of the control group. Also, these results imply that as the level of the learning engagement is higher, the test performance is also higher. Similarly, one study claims that low level of classroom engagement leads to negative effects on course performance and learning process (Wang et al., 2014).

Correlation of Learning Engagement and Post-test Performance of Experimental Group with the application of @ClassPoint

The Pearson Correlation analysis between the learning engagement and the post-test performance of the experimental group of Science 10 – Physics is presented below (Table 4.11).

Table 13. *Correlation of learning engagement and post-test performance of experimental group that uses @ClassPoint (n=47)*

Control Group	r- value	p-value
Learning Engagement Post Test	0.732	0.000

*Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed)

The correlation of the experimental group's learning engagement and post-test performance has an r-value of 0.732 with a p-value of 0.000 based on p-value < 0.01 level of correlation. These results indicate that there is a significant relationship between learning engagement of the experimental group with their post-test performance. These results implies that as the level of students' learning

engagement is higher, their test scores are also higher.

The result of the study is consistent with an earlier study's finding that higher levels of student engagement are associated with better academic performance (Dyer, 2015). According to a different study (Handelsman et al., 2015), student participation in the classroom is one of the key predictors of student accomplishment. Similar to the previous study, another one (Hao Lei et al., 2018) demonstrates a reasonably substantial and favorable link between total student engagement and academic attainment.

Conclusions

Based on their learning engagement, the experimental group is higher than in the control group. It is enhanced in the experimental group through the use of the @ClassPoint tool in the teaching process. Based on test performance, the experimental group performed better than the control group. These results confirm that the application of @ClassPoint tool as an intervention strategy integrated in the experimental group enhances the learners' academic performance. In both groups, their learning engagement is strongly correlated with their test performance. The application of @ClassPoint as an intervention strategy is effective in enhancing both the students' learning engagement and academic performance in Science -10 Physics.

It is recommended for the Science courses at various levels in the secondary academic program that @ClassPoint as an intervention technique is utilizable specially to enhance student engagement and academic performance. Since the present study has utilized the online version of the @ClassPoint, future studies may utilize this present online 1.0 version, or its latest offline 2.0 version.

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